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METABOLIC-ASSOCIATED STEATOTIC LIVER DISEASE (LITERATURE REVIEW)

Abstract

Metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD) is one of the most prevalent chronic liver diseases worldwide and is considered the hepatic manifestation of metabolic syndrome. The disease is characterized by excessive fat accumulation in hepatocytes in the absence of significant alcohol consumption or other secondary causes of hepatic steatosis. The main risk factors include obesity, insulin resistance, type 2 diabetes mellitus, dyslipidemia, and arterial hypertension.

Insulin resistance, lipid metabolism disorders, oxidative stress, chronic low-grade inflammation, and mitochondrial dysfunction play a central role in the pathogenesis of MASLD. Disease progression may lead to the development of metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis (MASH), liver fibrosis, cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma.

Diagnosis is based on a combination of clinical, laboratory, and instrumental methods, including ultrasound imaging, elastography, and non-invasive fibrosis markers. The cornerstone of treatment is lifestyle modification, weight reduction, correction of metabolic disturbances, and pharmacological management of comorbid conditions.

Thus, MASLD is a multifactorial progressive disease with a high risk of complications, requiring early diagnosis and a comprehensive approach to treatment and prevention.

Keywords: *metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD), metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis (MASH), insulin resistance, hepatic steatosis, liver fibrosis, metabolic syndrome, type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity.*

In recent years, the terms “metabolic-associated fatty liver disease (MAFLD)” and “metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD)” have been introduced to improve the reflection of metabolic dysregulation in this patient population, as well as to avoid the negative and stigmatizing terms “non-alcoholic” and “fatty” [2]. Metabolic dysfunction associated with steatotic liver disease (MASLD) has become the most common chronic liver disease worldwide, affecting ~25%–30% of the adult population, with a higher prevalence in individuals with obesity and type 2 diabetes. Among reported cases of MASLD, the prevalence is consistently higher in men than in women, and the global incidence has increased by ~50% over the past two decades, reflecting the global rise in obesity and the metabolic syndrome. MASLD encompasses a spectrum of liver pathologies ranging from simple steatosis to steatohepatitis, fibrosis and cirrhosis. Despite its high prevalence, the heterogeneity of disease progression and the relative lack of approved pharmacological

therapy pose challenges for effective clinical management [1]. There is evidence to suggest an association between MASLD and coronary heart disease (CHD), heart failure (HF), atrial fibrillation (AF), stroke, peripheral artery disease (PAD), and chronic kidney disease (CKD), although the data for HF, AF, stroke, and PAD are smaller. Physicians should consider the relationship between MASLD and cardiovascular disease in their daily practice. Based on this knowledge and current guidelines, they should also assess and manage risks and comorbidities in such patients. It is important to further investigate the impact of MASLD on cardiovascular outcomes, knowledge that will help clarify the clinical implications of this “new” hepatic entity [2].

The purpose of the assignment and research. Metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD), which includes an inflammatory subtype of metabolic dysfunction associated with steatohepatitis, is a prominent cause of chronic liver disease with systemic consequences. Insulin resistance,

obesity, and dyslipidemia cause MASLD in more than 30% of adults. This is a global health problem. During the transition from MASLD to MASH, liver inflammation and fibrosis increase, leading to cirrhosis, hepatocellular carcinoma, and extrahepatic complications such as CVD, CKD, and sarcopenia. The effect of MASLD on MASH is mediated by mechanisms that include inflammation, oxidative stress, dysbiosis, and genetic predisposition. Advances in diagnostic nomenclature over the past few years have shifted the emphasis from NAFLD to MASLD, focusing on the metabolic etiology and de-stigmatizing the alcohol-related condition. Epidemiological data show great geographic variability and an increasing prevalence in younger populations, particularly in regions with high-carbohydrate diets and central obesity. Lifestyle modification is currently considered the main approach to the management of MASLD. This may include dietary intervention, exercise and weight loss management. Pharmaceutical treatment primarily targets metabolic dysfunction, with promising findings for GLP-1 receptor agonists, pioglitazone, and SGLT-2 inhibitors, which may improve both hepatic and systemic outcomes. However, this still depends on well-integrated multidisciplinary care models given the complex relationships between MASLD and its extrahepatic effects. Identifying complications at an early stage, developing precision medicine strategies, and exploring new therapeutic targets will be crucial factors in improving their outcomes. This review discusses the systemic nature of MASLD and calls for multi-stakeholder collaboration to reduce its far-reaching health impact and our quest to understand its pathological mechanisms. Thus, the collective effort required to address MASLD spans the domains of public health, clinical care, and research to effectively curb its rapidly increasing burden [3].

Materials and methods. This study was performed as a systematic review of the literature aimed at summarizing the current scientific data on metabolic-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD). The analysis of the literature was carried out in accordance with international standards of a systematic review, in compliance with the principles of evidence-based medicine and structured data synthesis. The search for scientific publications was carried out in PubMed/MEDLINE, Scopus and Google Scholar databases, using keywords and terms: "metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease", "MASLD", "steatohepatitis", "metabolic syndrome", "epidemiology", "pathogenesis", "therapy". The search covered the period from 2019 to May 2025, focusing on the last 3 years of publications to reflect the most current scientific data.

The following were involved in the review:

1. original clinical studies,
2. systematic reviews and meta-analyses,
3. review articles published in peer-reviewed international journals with available full texts or extended abstracts in English.

The selection of articles was carried out with a preliminary check of relevance by title and abstract, after which the full texts were evaluated according to the following criteria:

- compliance with the topic of MASLD and its key aspects (epidemiology, pathogenesis, clinical manifestations, therapy);

- availability of a description of the methodology, results and discussion in the IMRaD format

(Introduction, Methods, Results, Discussion);

- high scientific level of the evidence base (randomized trials, multicenter studies, reviews with an assessment of the quality of included works).

Statistical analysis of epidemiological indicators was performed on the basis of data from selected studies from PubMed: calculation of the prevalence of MASLD in the general population and groups with metabolic disorders, with 95% confidence intervals established where provided by the authors of the original papers.

Evaluation of mechanistic and therapeutic aspects was carried out by cascading thematic synthesis of data with subdivision into key blocks: molecular mechanisms, cardiometabolic relationships, influence of lifestyle modifications and pharmacological interventions. The obtained results were summarized in comparison tables. The sources were grouped by the level of evidence and the quality of the methodology in accordance with the recommendations of international guidelines and scientific practice, which meets the general requirements of the Colloquium-journal regarding scientific rigor.

Presentation of the main material.

Epidemiology and prevalence. The global increase in obesity-related metabolic disorders has made metabolic dysfunction associated with steatotic liver disease (MASLD) one of the most common chronic liver diseases worldwide. Despite growing concern, the exact pathogenesis of MASLD remains unclear, and no definitive treatments have been developed. Therefore, the need for comprehensive research on MASLD is more critical than ever. Understanding disease mechanisms may lay the foundation for the discovery of new therapeutics and may facilitate the development of diagnostic tools that allow early detection and intervention of MASLD. Studies have revealed a multifactorial etiology for MASLD, suggesting that potential therapeutic strategies should be considered from different perspectives. This review delves into the pathogenesis of MASLD, current diagnostic approaches, potential therapeutic targets, clinical trial status of new drugs, and the most promising treatments available today. By focusing on therapeutic targets, the aim is to offer fresh insights and guidance for future research in the treatment of MASLD [4].

Pathogenesis and mechanisms. MASLD results from metabolic dysfunction with an emphasis on insulin resistance, obesity, dyslipidemia, and systemic inflammation. Pathogenetic mechanisms include:

- excessive accumulation of triglycerides in hepatocytes;

- dysregulation of lipogenesis, which leads to steatosis;

- participation of intestinal microbiota in pathogenesis by influencing metabolites and barrier function;

- oxidative stress and inflammatory response.

A review in the International Journal of Molecular Medicine describes these key mechanisms, including their impact on the progression from simple steatosis to active steatohepatitis and fibrosis [5].

Clinical manifestations and comorbid conditions. MASLD is often asymptomatic in its early stages, but may have nonspecific symptoms such as fatigue or discomfort in the right hypochondrium. Also, the disease is associated with a significant risk of cardiovascular disease (CVD), which is an important component of systemic consequences for patients. MASLD is associated not only with individual liver pathologies, but also with cardiometabolic and metabolic comorbid conditions, including heart failure, coronary artery disease, and a significant increase in cardiovascular risk [10].

Diagnosis of MASLD

- Hepatic steatosis (using imaging, biomarkers, or biopsy)

- At least 1 cardiometabolic risk factor
- Limited history of alcohol use (no more than 2 drinks per day for women or 3 drinks per day for men)
- Serology to rule out hepatitis B and C

The diagnosis of MASLD should be suspected in patients with the metabolic syndrome or metabolic risk factors (usually obesity, type 2 diabetes or high fasting plasma glucose, hypertension, and dyslipidemia), a limited history of alcohol consumption, and patients with unexplained laboratory abnormalities suggestive of liver disease.

A formal diagnosis of MASLD requires evidence of hepatic steatosis and at least 1 cardiometabolic risk factor (1). Cardiometabolic risk factors important to meet diagnostic criteria include at least 1 of these 5 factors:

- BMI > 25 kg/m² (BMI > 23 in Asian populations) or waist circumference > 94 cm (men) or 80 cm (women)
- Fasting serum glucose > 100 mg/dL or HgbA1c > 5.7% or type 2 diabetes or current treatment of type 2 diabetes
- Blood pressure > 130/85 mm/Hg. or is currently being treated with antihypertensive drugs
- Triglycerides > 150 or currently being treated with lipid-lowering therapy
- HDL cholesterol 40 mg/dL (men) or HDL 50 mg/dL (women) or currently being treated with lipid medications (2)

The diagnosis of MASH requires evidence of liver inflammation as well as steatosis, and requires a biopsy showing histological evidence of hepatocellular injury and inflammation with or without fibrosis. Cirrhosis may also be present [6].

Treatment. Lifestyle changes are recommended for all patients with MASLD, even without MASH, because these patients have metabolic abnormalities and are at risk for developing cardiovascular disease. Recommended weight loss is 3% to 5% for simple steatosis and 7% to 10% for NASH. Adequate control of risk factors, such as hyperlipidemia with statins (which also protect against cardiovascular risks) and hypertension, as well as adequate glycemic control, is

required. Resmetirom (thyroid hormone receptor beta agonist):

Resmetirom is used for patients with MASH and stage F2 or F3 fibrosis without significant weight loss. Cirrhotic patients were excluded from previous clinical trials, but ongoing studies are evaluating its safety in this group. The recommended dose for patients weighing less than 100 kg is 80 mg orally once daily; for those weighing 100 kg or more, 100 mg orally once daily should be administered. Before prescribing resmetir, clinicians should evaluate potential drug interactions. Resmetir should not be used with OATP 1B1/1B3 inhibitors (eg cyclosporine) or strong CYP2C8 inhibitors (eg gemfibrozil) [3].

Vitamin E is recommended for patients with MASH (fibrosis stage 2 or higher) who do not have diabetes at a dose of 800 IU daily. The risks and benefits should be discussed with the patient, as high doses of vitamin E may slightly increase all-cause mortality based on observational studies [7].

The incidence and prevalence of nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is steadily increasing worldwide, with an enormous social and economic burden. Recently, NAFLD and nonalcoholic steatohepatitis have been renamed and redefined as metabolic dysfunction associated with steatotic liver disease (MASLD) and steatohepatitis (metabolic dysfunction associated with steatohepatitis (MASH)), which result from an imbalance between metabolic and inflammatory stress (mainly due to adipose tissue dysfunction and insulin resistance) and defense mechanisms and restoration of steatosis liver. Once MASLD progresses to end-stage liver disease, treatment efficacy becomes limited and may require liver transplantation. Early detection and intervention are critical. Therefore, lifestyle modification is the cornerstone of its management. Timely consideration of bariatric surgery should be given to patients who meet certain criteria. A multidisciplinary approach is warranted, starting with the concept that MASLD/MASH is at the heart of the cardiovascular-hepatic metabolic syndrome. In some cases, pharmacological treatment can complement lifestyle modification. Several drugs used to treat cardiometabolic comorbidities have some potential efficacy in slowing the progression of Down's disease, and some have demonstrated efficacy on histologic endpoints that are likely to translate into long-term clinical benefits. Thus, optimizing the use of these drugs within their licensed indications is of paramount importance for patients with MASLD. Several specific MASH drugs are on the horizon and are likely to enrich our therapeutic arsenal in the near future, especially in non-cirrhotic stages disease. Much work remains to be done to understand the specific features of MASH cirrhosis and to develop effective treatments for this stage of the disease [8].

Conclusions. Metabolic-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD) is a common chronic liver disease closely associated with metabolic syndrome, obesity, and diabetes. Current evidence suggests that MASLD may remain asymptomatic in the early stages, but gradually progress to steatohepatitis (MASH), fibrosis,

cirrhosis, and an increased risk of hepatocellular carcinoma. The diagnosis of MASLD is based on a combination of clinical findings, laboratory findings, and noninvasive methods to assess liver fibrosis, such as FIB 4 and elastography. Liver biopsy remains the gold standard in difficult cases. Treatment of MASLD is primarily aimed at lifestyle modification: weight loss, a balanced diet and physical activity. Control of metabolic risk factors (glycemia, lipid profile, blood pressure) significantly improves the prognosis of patients. Among pharmacological strategies promising are GLP 1 agonists and new THR β receptor modifiers, but there is no universal therapy yet. The prognosis of MASLD largely depends on early detection and comprehensive management of the patient. Systematic monitoring of liver functions, assessment of fibrosis and correction of accompanying metabolic disorders can significantly reduce the risk of disease progression and cardiovascular complications.

Therefore, MASLD is an important global health problem that requires a multidisciplinary approach, including early diagnosis, individualized therapy and systematic monitoring of patients with metabolic risks [9].

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